

NFDI4Ing's success story 2022

Table of contents

Introduction.....	i
Archetypes.....	i
ALEX – bespoke experiments with high variability of setups	i
BETTY – engineering research software	ii
CADEN – provenance tracking of physical samples & data samples	iii
DORIS – high performance measurement & computation.....	iv
ELLEN – extensive and heterogeneous data requirements	iv
FRANK – many participants & simultaneous devices.....	v
GOLO – field data & distributed systems.....	vi
BASE SERVICES.....	vii
Quality assurance in RDM processes and metrics for FAIR data.....	vii
Research software development.....	vii
Metadata and terminology services	viii
Repositories and Storage.....	ix
Overall NFDI software architecture – data security and sovereignty	ix
Community-based training on enabling data-driven science and FAIR data	x
Automated data and knowledge discovery in engineering literature.....	xi
COMMUNITY CLUSTERS (CCs).....	xi
NFDI4Ing conference 2022	xi
Ing.grid – FAIR Data Management in Engineering Sciences	xii
Community Meetings	xii
Acknowledgement.....	xiii

Introduction

NFDI4Ing is a consortium from the first round of applications of Germany's National Research Data Infrastructure (Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur – NFDI). NFDI4Ing's goal is to make the data accruing throughout the entire engineering research process sustainably accessible, which means in a citable form according to [FAIR](#) principles and under licenses that are as free as possible. The funding programme has started as of October 1st 2020, and after looking back on their accomplishments from 2021 ([link](#)), our Task Areas (TAs) now look back on their accomplishments from 2022. For details regarding the work programme, please refer to our [published proposal](#).

Archetypes

[ALEX – bespoke experiments with high variability of setups](#)

Data and their analysis always play a crucial role in research and science. In recent years, especially with steadily increasing computational power and the advances in the field of artificial intelligence (AI), the importance of high-quality data has continued to grow. In this context, entire research fields and committees exclusively concern with improving data and their quality to maximize the potential of their use. However, the use of AI in industry also offers enormous potential for companies. For example, in case of condition monitoring tasks, an early detection of damages and wear down of parts or machines can avoid unplanned machine downtime costs. Instead, maintenance can then be scheduled according to predicted maintenance, and downtimes can thus be minimized.

NFDI4Ing's success story 2022

A basic requirement for a successful application of AI in the industrial context is a solid database with high quality data, e.g., from the production process itself, but also from testing processes. However, the practical application of AI algorithms often fails due to insufficient data quality due to missing or incomplete annotation of the data, incomplete data acquisition, problems when linking measurement data to the corresponding manufactured products, or a lack of synchronization between different data acquisition systems. Furthermore, in industry, data are typically acquired continuously without saving relevant metadata. In addition, this often leads to a brute force approach, which tries to use all acquired data. In general, large data sets are subsequently difficult to manage and their use is computationally expensive. A knowledge driven approach can efficiently use resources and increase the information density within the data, e.g., by reducing the amount of used sensor data due to process knowledge. By recording data in a targeted manner, redundancies can be avoided. However, linking knowledge and data is difficult and a known problem in many companies. In companies, the necessary process knowledge is often limited to a few individuals and cannot be easily accessed by colleagues. In the worst case, the process knowledge is lost if the specialist leaves the company.

For these cases and to retain the knowledge, the concept "PIA – Personal Information Assistant for Data Analysis" has been developed. PIA is an open-source framework, based on Angular, a platform for building mobile and desktop web applications, which runs locally on a server and can be accessed via the intranet. It allows companies to easily access their data as well as process knowledge, to link both and gain further insights into their manufacturing process and the acquired data. PIA is developed in accordance with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-

usable) data principles widely applied in scientific research and aims to transfer these principles to the industry.

At the NFDI4Ing Conference, we showed how the PIA framework is applied to a part of an assembly line demonstrator, which assembles a specific product in several variants, with the focus on screwing processes. In general, PIA provides a checklist as well as a knowledge base which supports users performing a data analysis project on brownfield assembly lines and increase data quality. The checklist is based on the Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM) and provides must-checkboxes and best-practice-checkboxes, as well as tips and hints, to obtain high quality data. Using the modular approach of Angular, PIA can be easily extended to further processes or products and adapted to companies' individual regulations and requirements.

BETTY – engineering research software

In 2022, BETTY continued to focus on the key aspects of sustainable research software: findability, reproducibility and quality assurance. Our vision is that researchers in engineering produce validated software of high quality, that can be found, reused and built upon by other researchers. Finding suitable research software lies at the foundation of this vision, and we are happy to announce that a first prototype of BETTY's (Re)Searchengine has gone live at <http://nfdi4ing.rz-housing.tu-clausthal.de/>. This service is continuously improved, and in ongoing efforts we are evaluating how to interconnect it with other NFDI4Ing services.

When reusing the research software of others, a first step may be to try to reproduce published results that were obtained with the software. In order for this to work with minimal effort on the (re-)user side, the computation of the results has to be automated in a pipeline that can be

NFDI4Ing's success story 2022

easily triggered. To this end, we have looked into a number of workflow tools in the context of the special interest group „Tools for describing, reproducing and reusing scientific workflows“. We have evaluated these tools regarding features that simplify both the creation of workflows as well as their (re-)usage. A full report of our evaluation has been submitted to the *ing.grid* journal ([link](#)).

Building upon the software of others requires access to the source code and poses additional requirements on its quality. In this context, reliability, flexibility, extensibility and readability of the source code are of primary importance. The software engineering community has come up with a variety of solutions to these issues, drawn from decades of experience. We have extracted those that we deem most relevant for research software, and have compiled them into easily-accessible teaching material for lectures ([link](#)) or intensive one-week PhD seminars ([link](#)).

Finally, software quality also includes that its functionality is thoroughly tested. In engineering, which often involves numerical simulations of physical processes, a very useful technique is *regression-testing*. In a regression test, the results of a computation are compared against reference data that was obtained with the software at an earlier stage. This makes sure that the developers are notified if a change to the source code produces unexpected deviations in the results that the software produces. To facilitate this, we have developed a tool that can carry out regression tests for a variety of file formats by extracting the data fields from corresponding files, and (fuzzy-)comparing them against those of the reference data. The tool is available on PyPI ([link](#)), and can further be used via a GitHub Action ([link](#)).

CADEN – provenance tracking of physical samples & data samples

The year 2022 meant evolutionary changes as well as completely new directions in CADEN.

The evolutionary changes involve SciMesh, our knowledge graph schema for scientific workflows and results. By and large, its foundation now has its final shape, which means that electronic lab notebooks (ELNs) can export, share, and import their content in and from SciMesh knowledge graphs. What does this mean for you? Any ELN supporting SciMesh can enrich its data with live data from other ELNs. This supports and scientist who works in collaborations with external researchers with their own remote ELN. Of course, virtually no ELN supports SciMesh yet but the JuliaBase prototype proves the validity of the SciMesh approach. We are working on further prototypes.

The new directions extend the possibilities to share and publish scientific data in a more ad-hoc fashion than with SciMesh knowledge graphs alone. We work together with other ELN developers in the “ELN consortium” and develop there a special RO-Crate profile that contains the RO-Crate mandatory data as well as the sample's complete SciMesh graph. This will enable you to export a sample's complete data (raw data files, experimental parameters, analysis data, comments, papers, plots, etc) into a single container file that you can send, upload, or archive. All of that using a well-specified, open, reusable file format that builds on existing standards.

However, we still fail to get in intensive and broad contact with our customers. Our customers, they are the scientists out their with a lot of data of their samples and workpieces, and with urgent need to manage that data usefully and efficiently. If you are one of them – get in touch with us! Visit SciMesh's website and send us your thoughts about it. We

NFDI4Ing's success story 2022

are happy to arrange spontaneous online meetings, too. And, in case you are an IT-savvy, install the JuliaBase prototype (in particular, the “graphs” branch) and kick the tyres. You may submit everything you observe in GitHub issues, or share it with us in an online meeting.

DORIS – high performance measurement & computation

Task Area DORIS designs transferable research data management concepts and tools for data from high-performance measurement and computation (HPMC). In order to standardize and facilitate RDM for our peer group, we provide solutions for the complete data life cycle.

-Metadata extraction: To collect metadata, especially in the stages of planning, creating/collecting and processing/analyzing, DORIS released the python-written metadata crawler [HOMER](#) (HPMC tool for Ontology-based Metadata Extraction and Re-use). It allows to automatically retrieve relevant research metadata from script-based workflows on HPC systems. The tool offers a flexible approach to metadata collection, as the metadata scheme can be read out from an ontology file. One major factor of making data FAIR is a controlled vocabulary / common terminology. Therefore, DORIS provides a first, user-based concept for a HPMC sub-ontology within the framework of [Metadate4Ing](#).

-Community Support and Teaching: The success of DORIS' Measures depends on acceptance and usage of RDM concepts and tools within the HPMC community. To transfer the obtained knowledge and outcome, and to promote preexisting or newly developed tools, DORIS regularly provides community-based training, workshops and established an undergraduate module on RDM in engineering sciences. Within the recent training and education activities, DORIS managed to lecture more than 100 persons directly, the published training material already passed 500 (*unique*) downloads.

iv | nfdi4ing.de

In this context, we organise a DORIS online workshop on March 28, 2022. The workshop is addressed at users of HPC computing centers producing large amount of (immobile) data and personnel in research-data management ([link](#)).

-Obstacles: DORIS is currently strengthening its efforts in advocating simplified access for third party users to HPC facilities to enable data access and re-use. In general, a strong dependence on service providers, their policies and infrastructure (computing centers, software development) can be seen as a major obstacle.

-Outreach to HPC centers: The primary focus of DORIS lies on the (national) tier 1 computing centers, but we are trying to establish an improved involvement of tier 2 centers or the NHR Alliance (National High Performance Computing). Therefore, we would like to invite scientists in RDM from tier 2 centers to contact us for future collaborations in infrastructure, data management or community support. Please subscribe to our [newsletter](#) or [contact](#) us directly to receive further updates and enable possible collaborations.

ELLEN – extensive and heterogeneous data requirements

In the second year of the ELLEN Task Area, we succeeded in developing the DataDesc ecosystem, which aids in the description of data models of software interfaces using machine-actionable metadata. Based on a semantic framework that enables the detailed annotation and linking of software and datasets, we created a specialized metadata schema. The ability to locate and compare research software that satisfies specific needs, as well as to seamlessly incorporate research software into existing research processes, will improve as more researchers describe their research software using DataDesc.

NFDI4Ing's success story 2022

In addition, we developed an exchange format and support tools for the easy collection and automated publishing of software documentation on various publication platforms, such as SwaggerHub, ReadTheDocs, and the Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG). Furthermore, a concept for a search engine for research software was formulated, providing an integrated search functionality across individual publication platforms and code repositories utilizing semantic descriptions and federated queries.

Over the last year, the activities in the ELLEN Task Area have strengthened the established connection to the research area of Energy Systems Analysis (ESA) and created new connections to the NFDI4Energy consortium. Also, the collaborations with Task Area BETTY and the community clusters CC-42 and CC-43 were deepened. In particular, we established an ORKG observatory for ESA, cooperated closely with NFDI4Energy on the DataDesc approach, worked with BETTY on a joint ReSearch Engine, and presented DataDesc with its underlying ideas and benefits, together with the community clusters.

FRANK – many participants & simultaneous devices

"Will the framework be a program or a guideline? Should it be an online tool or some local instance? The tracks for those decisions are already laid out!" This were the last sentences of last year's success story and what a lot has changed since then! First of all, to answer the two questions raised, resolving a cliff-hanger one year long: The proposed tool should not be a guideline in a paper form but rather a RDM-supporting tool which is implemented as a webtool, enabling collaboration.

-What will this tool be? With this out the way, it should be clarified what this tool is, what it will look like and how far it has come by now. First of all, the name should be clarified. The tool is called Joint Assistant for Research in Versatile Engineering Sciences, or in short: Jarves. Jarves aims

v | nfdi4ing.de

to enhance RDM in engineering by guiding researchers through the RDM process along their everyday research, giving them needed information on RDM at just the right time. This not only includes linking to RDM-trainings provided by Base Service S-6 any beyond, but also decision support inside of Jarves, for example suggesting tools to use in RDM with reasons why one tool should be preferred over another.

However, this only solves the problem of researchers not knowing how to deal with RDM, not that it is often considered additional work rather than something valuable. This issue is also going to be addressed by Jarves, at least concerning the overhead caused by lack of RDM-knowledge and unconnected services. Currently the application of RDM is hindered by multiple unlinked services. For example: When adding a project in RDMO to fill out a DMP, one has to completely fill out the project information, just to do the same again when adding a project to Coscine. Jarves currently works on interlinking both of these services.

-Okay, but how can I benefit from that? A potential workflow within Jarves could start with the creation of a project. After filling out the information on the project, Jarves will hint you towards the creation of a DMP and also recommend which tool you could use to do so. If you are unfamiliar with DMPs, do not worry: Jarves provides links to training materials on this and other topics. Assuming RDMO is your DMP-tool of choice, you select it and Jarves sends the project information to RDMO. There you can add additional information, filling out RDMOs questionnaires. Let's assume you also add the info, that you will most probably collect personal data of some survey participants later on. Months go by and you have almost finished your project, not yet having checked the box or clicked the button (design decision pending) saying, "Store data and metadata". Wanting to archive your data, you get the

NFDI4Ing's success story 2022

notification that Coscine might be the best tool for you to use on your specific project. You then proceed to the archiving step and let Jarves create your project within Coscine, so you just have to upload your files there. Later, you proceed to upload your files to a data repository to provide your data along with your publication. But suddenly a notification pops up. It reminds you that you have mentioned that you wanted to collect personal data and prompts you to check to not upload any personal data or gather the corresponding consent forms. This way you can just link your chosen repository (which Jarves might have told you to use) to the publication without worries, that you might run into legal trouble. However, Jarves will never permit anything, so that you can disobey any of these prompts at any time.

This potential workflow sketches out the idea of how and why Jarves might be useful to researchers. Hopefully you are now eager to use this tool right away, but we have to slow you down there a little bit. Jarves is currently in the early development phase, aiming for a MVP release within 2023. MVP meaning a “minimal viable product”, that demonstrates certain functionality but not all of it. This should give us opportunity to collect and implement feedback earlier in the development process.

-Sign me up! When can I use this? Right now, Jarves has proven its feasibility in terms of architecture, relying on a backend implementation in Python and based on Django and a frontend written in Angular. There are some pages already, also with build in functionality, giving the general idea of how everything may come together. As for the database we are currently using the SQLite that comes with Django but would like to shift this to an ontology-based approach, which should enable us to use metadata4ing as base for our data model. The next big steps for Jarves

will be the restructuring of the database, the implementation of the data model and the invocation of RDMO and Coscine connectivity. The later one is already conceptualized but needs to be implemented next. This sums up the activities planned for Jarves in 2023.

GOLO – field data & distributed systems

In 2022, the three project partners LUH, DFKI and TUD continued the development of a digital twin for the management of research field data within Task Area GOLO. There were some administrative changes in addition to the content work. In August 2022 Iryna Mozgova and in October 2022 our spokesperson Hauke Dierend left the project. The position as group leader in TA GOLO was taken over by Philipp Findling from LUH.

We compared different technical systems to derive a set of necessary data for the digital twin. Classification of data analysis techniques continued. To get a better sense of the needs of potential GOLO users, we designed a questionnaire on the handling and use of field data and disseminated it to the engineering community. The evaluation is ongoing, with results expected in 2023. We also plan to expand this questionnaire and disseminate it to other application areas.

Several tools for managing research field data are currently under development: we have written a manual for preparing and conducting field experiments that focuses on data collection. This includes a list of recommended tools for documenting field conditions and a metadata schema for describing field experiments. We are also preparing a handbook for engineering systems development based on field data.

A catalog of quality metrics for sensor data has been published online. This work was accompanied by TA GOLO's participation within the Special

NFDI4Ing's success story 2022

Interest Group (SIG) Quality Assurance and Fair Metrics with a guest lecture and workshop. Our publications also include a conference paper on managing research field data within the digital twin concept.

A large number of field tests were conducted at LUH using the developed experimental vehicle. The camera and lidar sensors were used individually as well as in combination. Some of the recorded data have already been analyzed and will be used in the future to train object recognition algorithms. The publication of a data set is also in prospect if possible. Regarding the personnel planning, a new person will be hired by LUH at the beginning of the year 2023.

BASE SERVICES

Quality assurance in RDM processes and metrics for FAIR data

Since Sept. 2022, we provide a DMP Service at <https://rdmo.nfdi4ing.de> available for all interested researchers working in the engineering sciences. The Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO) assists researchers in the planning of their data management. We adapted the Open Source software to better support the specific needs of the engineering sciences. A step-by-step guide leads researchers through the process of creating a data management plan custom-made for their research project and to fulfil the requirements of funding agencies, especially of the DFG. The DMP template was designed based on an international survey and workshops in NFDI4Ing. By implementing DFN-AAI and ORCID login the tool also allows for cross-institutional collaboration. After 4 months running nearly 50 projects were already created in RDMO.

Also, a first version of a maturity model for data access management was developed and made available, oriented to the data life cycle phase

vii | nfdi4ing.de

access. Using a defined maturity structure enables researchers to evaluate data access in research projects. This maturity model has been published and is freely available ([link](#)). In addition to introduction slides on the use of maturity models and the scope of data access management, a checklist is also available for the complete assessment of the maturity level, which can be further extended and used for specific projects. In the further course, additional models oriented to the data life cycle will be developed and made available.

The Special Interest Group (SIG) Quality Assurance and Fair Metrics, founded by the BASE SERVICES Measure *quality assurance in RDM processes and metrics for FAIR data* together with the COMMUNITY CLUSTERS Measure *standardisation* in 2021, also intensified the exchange between interested parties and suppliers in this area. Thus, in 2022, content on topics such as fair metrics, research activities, and data management plans about quality assurance could be discussed and developed in lecture content and workshop content in a total of four quarterly meetings. In these meetings with an average of 30 interested scientists, much content from other Tas Areas within the consortium (e.g. Task Areas FRANK and GOLO) or even content from outside the consortium (e.g. SFB1153-Tailored Forming, EOSC) could be integrated and intensified within the meetings of this Special Interest Group.

Research software development

-Technische Universität Darmstadt: We run the Knowledge Base for development of scientific software for over a year by now. Therein we address the topics version control, continuous integration, test driven development and many more. This year we could improve the Knowledge Base as a website, overhaul some of the articles but our focus was on promoting our ideas and our service. We did so not only at the

NFDI4Ing's success story 2022

FOSDEM'22 but also at the TU9-Workshop "Data Stewardship goes Germany" and at the "Sustainable and Resilient Energy for Europe?!" Winter School 2022.

At the end of the year we started an experiment and we now offer weekly consultation hours for the Knowledge Base. We hope thereby to get to know our "customers" and their needs better and get their feedback. This could help us to even better help the community. The workflow not only is described in the Knowledge Base but also in a preprint ([link](#)), we went public with this year. We are looking forward to publish it as a journal paper in 2023.

-Universität Stuttgart: The NFDI4Ing JupyterHub (<https://jupyter.nfdi4ing.de>) that allows scientists to interactively execute code and enrich the code with text, figures and more (literate programming) is running in pilot operation for almost a year now. We have test users from Stuttgart and Hannover so far, but would like to invite further interested scientists to become test users to make this service as beneficial as possible.

In the last year, we worked on a use case together with the Institute of Engineering and Computational Mechanics (US) to enable using MATLAB via the JupyterHub and achieved two solutions: 1) Powered by the server proxy interface of Jupyter the MATLAB IDE can be used directly within the browser. 2) Based on the Script of Scripts computational environment ([link](#)) it is possible to execute MATLAB and Python code within the same Jupyter notebook. In this way, the collaboration of scientists with different programming language preferences is fostered.

Further, we are actively working in the NFDI Section Common Infrastructure WG RSE, bringing together all interested national

JupyterHub instances. In 2022 we initiated a joint website of all JupyterHubs as an entrypoint for researchers getting an overview and easily finding the right address for their Jupyter requirements.

-RWTH Aachen University: NFDI4Ing hosted four introductory workshops on the usage of Git and GitLab for the management of Research data. The workshop showed a total of 75 participants how they can make use of version control features provided by Git and the project management and collaboration features provided by GitLab to enhance the quality of their research data and research data management processes. While the workshop itself was held almost in the same way as in 2021, this year NFDI4Ing cooperated with NHR4CES to gain more visibility and reach out to an even broader community. Further workshops are planned throughout 2023 and will be continued in conjunction with NHR4CES.

[Metadata and terminology services](#)

The year 2022 marked a major step forward for the BASE SERVICES Measure *metadata and terminology services*, as prototypes or production systems of service offerings have now gone live at all three Tasks in this Measure. We have presented these services in numerous workshops, meetings, newsletters, and social media posts, and have been able to lay the groundwork for close contact with the technical research community. In particular, we were able to use concrete examples to show how the service chain of this Measure interlocks and provides added value in research data management. This was in part possible by the release of the Metadata Hub and its demonstrator application. In addition to the range of services that have emerged in the various tasks of this Measure, we can also announce that a first complete version of the M4I ontology has been completed and made available to the public. For the coming year, we aim at an even closer coupling of the services of this Measure

NFDI4Ing's success story 2022

and seek direct connection to other NFDI4Ing tools of solutions from the basic service but also the archetypes.

Repositories and Storage

The past year was a very successful year for the *BASE SERVICES Measure repositories and storage*. The Coscine research data management platform has been extended by a WORM (Write Once, Read Many) resource. Once data is stored in the WORM resource, it cannot be modified or deleted. Data storage is guaranteed for at least 10 years. Access to WORM storage has high entrance barriers and requires a application and review process. A "Science Led Research Data Storage Quotation and Allocation" process has been developed and established, similar in nature to what is already established in the HPC (High Performance Computing) environment. WORM storage systems, already well established in the healthcare, finance and banking sectors, represent an innovation in engineering. The first two potential use cases are the storage of completed and approved blueprints and CAD files, as well as compliance with regulatory requirements.

Transferring data to or from other institutions' storage systems can be challenging. We aim to lower that hurdle with the architectural design of a data transfer federation. The goal is to enable researchers to perform large-scale data transfers seamlessly between independent storage systems. Authentication and authorization of users are handled by OAuth2. We participate in federated AAI (Authorization and Authentication Infrastructure) efforts to enable access to users' data on other storage systems. WebDAV ensures a user-friendly data access and data transfer. FTS3 is used to handle the transfer of (potentially huge amounts of) data between different storage systems. This project is currently a proof of concept between the WebDAV endpoints of LSDF

(Large Scale Data Facility) at KIT. Moreover, there is a collaboration with SDS@hd (Scientific Data Storage) at Heidelberg University to connect SDS to the federation. Storage systems of other institutions will be able to join the federation in the future. Use cases include the transfer of data from HPC systems to long term storage, as well as to archival cold storage.

The Data Collections Explorer is an information system for the engineering sciences, providing an overview of relevant research data repositories, archives, databases, as well as datasets published individually outside of established structures. It was released at the Gesamtteammeeting in March 2022 and presented to all Task Areas in the following months. The Data Collections Explorer was demonstrated to a wider audience at the Community Meetings in September and November; it was also represented with a poster at the HMC Conference 2022 in October. Following these events, we saw an increased interest in the service both within and outside of NFDI4Ing. Throughout the year, the community contributed not only to a large part of the content, but also provided valuable feedback and feature requests. Motivated by this feedback, we began developing a new version of the Data Collections Explorer. As a first goal, we plan to provide API access and ease integration with existing community efforts.

Overall NFDI software architecture – data security and sovereignty

The overall NFDI Software Architecture stood again in the light of continuous cooperation between NFDI4Ing and the other NFDI consortia. As part of the work within the Task Area, NFDI4Ing chaired and contributed to the Working Group Identity and Access Management within the section Common Infrastructures (WG IAM). The WG IAM is the successor of the previously founded Task Force Tools for Authentication and Authorization Infrastructures (TFT AAI) which was adopted into the

NFDI4Ing's success story 2022

section Common Infrastructures. Within this newly formed working group Members of more than ten NFDI consortia and other well established bodies like ZKI and DFN coordinate their activities towards a common authentication and authorization infrastructure. As part of their work a group of experts within the WG IAM collected already existing architectures and software solutions (<https://doc.nfdi-aa1.de/>) that could eventually be used to form the NFDI AAI as part of an NFDI AAI base service.

Community-based training on enabling data-driven science and FAIR data

In 2022 the BASE SERVICES Measure *training and education* ([link](#)) together with the COMMUNITY CLUSTERS Measure *education* proceeded to bring basic RDM trainings to the engineering community. With the feedback we collected in 2021 and 2022, we are still continuously tailoring our education materials towards our community's needs. For example, one main aspect was to aim at more interactive training design, which we are currently addressing by turning our repository from static PDF files into web pages with interactive elements. (For technology enthusiasts: GitLab Pages.)

-Reuse instead of re-inventing the wheel: So what does this mean and how did we get there? To be honest, we are not the first who working on RDM trainings. Therefore – and in the RDM's spirit of reusing existing data – we built our trainings based upon existing materials (considering the respective license). In addition to this, we published a list of existing external training materials ([link](#), feel free to add more resources!). We might not be the first ones for RDM trainings in general, but – to our best knowledge – we are the first who create RDM trainings with a special focus on engineers: To achieve this, we integrate engineering-specific
x | nfdi4ing.de

examples and focus on engineer's needs and requirements in RDM. Since even our team can cover only a small part of the diverse areas of engineering, we are always looking for community input like training requirements, RDM-related examples and experiences, and illustrative anecdotes! Find our trainings at <https://git.rwth-aachen.de/nfdi4ing/education> accessible without registration.

-What's inside? With regards on the contents, we have developed training materials on different topics along the data life cycle and about data management plans (DMPs), which will be followed by cross-topic modules about licensing, metadata and more. All trainings are self-learning materials to enable an upskilling in RDM independent of time and space. As mentioned, the current static PDFs will be replaced in 2023 by webpages with additional interactive elements like videos, quizzes, animations and more. We are expecting to make the trainings more varied this way and to strengthen the learning effect by small exercises.

Trainings and teaching – especially for self-learning materials – should not be a 'one-way street': Therefore we added a mechanism that the community can provide feedback. (One more time for technology enthusiasts: GitLab Issues.) Doing so, everyone (registration required) can provide engineering examples and anecdotes or even point at potential mistakes in the content. For our team this is a quality-assurance mechanism and a way to improve our trainings based on the community's feedback. For the community such public feedback is a kind of quality indicator, similar to customer reviews in online shopping. This makes the one-way street of providing trainings bi-directional.

To publish this training offerings to the community in NFDI4Ing and beyond, we have organized several meetings of our Special Interest

NFDI4Ing's success story 2022

Group (SIG) and promoted the Education GitLab at NFDI4Ing community meetings. Feel free to check out our trainings and to contact us!

Automated data and knowledge discovery in engineering literature

In Task S-7-1 the efforts to provide machine readable literature for text and data mining applications were continued. A concept for the harvesting process as well as the provision of the literature has been developed and its implementation was started. As a first step, CrossRef metadata files for the articles of several MDPI open access journals were harvested. This metadata harvesting process is the prerequisite to be able to continuously harvest and provide also the full text documents which are provided by MDPI via an FTP server. A concept for the provision of the documents via a DSpace repository and an eXist XML database was developed and first internal tests conducted.

The aim of S-7-2 was to provide guidelines for Text and Data Mining (TDM) for scientists which explain the current legal basis for performing TDM on scientific publications in Germany. This task was completed in Q4 of 2022. The guidelines are published under an Open-Access-Licence CC by 3.0 Germany and ready to use ([link](#)). The Guidelines describe if and how TDM for scientific purposes may be performed on scientific literature on the basis of the new German statutory exceptions of copyright law or licences and which risks may occur. The last section describes how publications may be used for TDM if neither a statutory exception nor a contractual permission applies.

The Guidelines concentrate only on the question whether TDM may be performed or not. To provide guidance on legal questions of institutions regarding the provision of TDM services for scientists not addressed by the guidelines, a workshop will be organized in Q2 of 2023.

COMMUNITY CLUSTERS (CCs)

NFDI4Ing conference 2022

This year's NFDI4Ing conference 2022 "Unifying the Understanding of RDM in Engineering Science" on October 26 and 27 was hosted by WZL of the RWTH Aachen University. The conference went for a more scientific approach, aiming for a structured review process and awards (along with the prizes money) as incentives for researchers to hand in contributions. Therefore, a double-blind peer-review process along with an expert review were performed on all 43 submissions. The best-reviewed contributions were then nominated for the awards, two of the nominees were even nominated for both awards. However, it was not possible to win both with just one contribution. The final awards have been based on the presentations at the conference, which were evaluated by a jury of five members. Each jury member represented one of the five NFDI4Ing communities (mechanical and industrial engineering, thermal and process engineering, materials science and engineering, computer science, systems and electrical engineering, and construction engineering and architecture).

Wendy (Pengyin) Shan could be determined as the winner of the NFDI4Ing Award 2022 for the best Conference Contribution with her contribution "Prepare RDM for Decentralized and Blockchain Based Data Source" and Rory Macneil has won the NFDI4Ing Award 2022 for the best RDM Solution with his demonstration "RSpace: An Electronic Lab Notebook designed to enhance FAIR workflows and FAIRification of research data". Both awards have been endowed with 500 €, sponsored by the WZL Aachen Stiftung. We congratulate the two award winners very warmly.

NFDI4Ing's success story 2022

The conference itself was divided into multiple parallel sessions ([link](#)): two presentations and one demonstration or workshop always took place simultaneously. The only occurrence when this structure was broken up was when the audience gathered in the main session to participate in the fringe programme or the key notes. Throughout the two days of the conference of the 297 registrations, a concurrent count of approximately 120 participants could be observed.

-On the first day, 1532 logins or changes between meeting rooms happened amongst the 178 unique participants. A total of 244 minutes in average amongst the participants was spent in the conference on the first day.

-The second day scored 1247 logins or changes between meeting rooms. The average time spent in the conference on the second day was 253 minutes per user.

The conference has also made a step towards reusability as the files used for automation have been provided to next year's organizing committee and will soon be publicly available ([link](#)). Along with that, all contributions to the conference are publicly available on Zenodo ([link](#)).

Ing.grid – FAIR Data Management in Engineering Sciences

Conference abstracts qualified for a special issue of ing.grid, which is currently in the making, so stay tuned on ing.grid's website ([link](#)) or (if you are very curious) head to the preprint server ([link](#))! On December 1st, Ing.grid published its first call-for-papers and has since been open for unsolicited submissions.

Community Meetings

With the first community meetings of the year the CC41 (Community Cluster 41 - mechanical and industrial engineering) hosted a rather big community meeting at March 3rd 2022. Two to three continuous parallel strands of lectures and demonstrations were a day-filling event. Session topics covered collaboration, rdm use cases, tools and metadata descriptions. On the same day the CC44 (Community Cluster 44 - computer science, systems and electrical engineering) held their community meeting with a single strand only split up in the last session. With key notes about open source and simulation of traffic data the meeting led into sessions regarding best practises, interdisciplinary data management and data literacy. The feedback gathered from these two events showed, that the participants would prefer a shorter and more condensed agenda, that is easier to fit into everyday business than a conference-like event.

This was taken into consideration when the second set of community meetings took place in autumn 2022. Here, CC42 and CC45 (COMMUNITY CLUSTERS 42 – thermal engineering and process engineering - and 45 - construction engineering and architecture) hosted their Community meetings on September 22nd and 23rd 2022 consisting of presentations and workshops featuring NFDI4Ing's task areas and services. Overarching topics were “data literacy & training”, “tools, services & methods” and “governance, curation and standards”. The design of these meetings was much more synchronised and streamlined than in the previous year, resulting in a much more consistent and uniform representation of the CCs. The duration was limited to around half a day, although 2 streams were still present in one of the meetings to accommodate all talks. Building on this foundation CC41 and CC43 (COMMUNITY CLUSTERS 41- mechanical and industrial engineering - and 43 - materials science and

NFDI4Ing's success story 2022

engineering) held their meetings at the end of September and November respectively, including their specific aspects.

The meetings gave participants as well as members of the consortium the chance to exchange experiences and requirements regarding services from NFDI4Ing. There were multiple examples where we as a consortium received valuable feedback. Some services found new users during the meetings.

It has been one of the key result of the community meetings that we perceived a strong desire for best practice examples. Furthermore data sets as benchmarks for the comparison with one's own data have been marked as a helpful service for scientists. These and other findings from past community meetings will be used on an ongoing basis to make the exchange with the community and the services of NFDI4Ing even more profitable.

You can find the schedules, abstracts and some materials related to the community meetings on our website nfdi4ing.de under *events & news > community meetings > past community meetings*.

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